

Reducing Power Consumption in Refrigeration Equipment using IoT Technology: The SmartFridge Project

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Refrigeration of food requires significant electricity amounts, equivalent to 50% of the consumption of food retail businesses. According to estimates by the International Institute of Refrigeration, the proportion of electricity consumed worldwide for cooling is 17% and, given the fact that the concentration of population in urban centers will rise to 85% from 75% today, the amount of energy consumed for refrigeration will further increase in the coming years. Unfortunately, this has a large environmental impact, as the required electricity is produced using mainly fossil fuels (solid, oil, petroleum, etc.). The main objective of the project is to reduce the energy consumption of refrigeration equipment and hence the energy footprint of food retail businesses through the implementation of intelligent control strategies concerning the operating temperature of the refrigeration cabinets. Reducing the required electricity will limit the emission of carbon dioxide gases into the atmosphere, meeting one of the European Union's key greenhouse gas mitigation policies, as well as climate change in general. Exploiting the partners' expertise, the project aims at designing and developing an innovative system for monitoring, recording, and storing temperature values, which adopts the Internet of Things (IoT) technology. This system will fully comply with the current legal and regulatory framework and will be the key tool for identifying potential energy savings on an annual basis by implementing coolant operating temperature control strategies.

During the operating hours of food retail businesses, there are significant losses in the cooling chambers due to the repeated opening and closing of refrigerators and freezers by customers. To quickly cover these losses and keep the air temperature inside the chambers within the desired limits, they are set to operate at lower-than-expected temperatures, which significantly increases their consumption. However, during the hours that the businesses are closed or when customer traffic is low (as shown by hourly transactions), the operation of the refrigeration equipment can be adjusted to higher levels without being any risk to food safety. Analyzing and processing the measurements will draw conclusions about the operation of the chambers and optimal settings to minimize their consumption will be proposed through energy reports. In addition, a separate subsystem will be implemented that will be connected to the compressor of each refrigeration chamber and, through the control of this function, will implement the strategies proposed by the system. A prerequisite for the success of the effort is the production of a low-cost product that will bring economic benefits from its commercial exploitation. In addition, installing it across a wide range of businesses will reduce their energy footprint, which is the demand for the proposed solution, as well as their operating costs by saving electricity.

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